

A privacy preserving Health Data Space approach for federated machine learning

Alessandro Bassi¹ and Konstantinos Koutsopoulos²

¹ Eurescom GmbH
Heidelberg, Germany
bassi@eurescom.eu

² Qualtek SPRL
Brussels, Belgium
k.koutsopoulos@qualtek.eu

Abstract

In this paper, we present the key concepts, principles and architecture approach of the EU Project PAROMA-MED. The project works on a novel hybrid cloud approach, with an elevated role of the edge, that introduces and utilizes advanced privacy preserving solutions. The overall objective is to accelerate the adoption of personal data federation on top of which Federated ML scenarios can be easily executed. The approach focuses on the establishment of high degree of trust between data owner and data management infrastructure so that consent in data processing is given by means of functional and enforceable options applicable at all levels of workloads and processes

1 Introduction

The project is targeting the exploitation of data, through Federated Machine Learning, in the medical sector which is highly sensitive regarding data protection but with huge potential regarding value creation for all the society. The project acknowledges the fact that GDPR has defined strict guidelines regarding the ways data must be treated on the basis of the data subject's fundamental rights. However, it is of concern that adherence to such rules is merely related to certain obligations which theoretically must be in effect and they may only serve for post incident (data breach) responsibility and liability resolution. In this context, PAROMA-MED, by focusing on i) complete transparency and control regarding all the flows and pipelines in which personal data are involved and ii) continuous attestation of the participating entities in any transaction, is proposing an innovative concept, aspired as "Functional GDPR", according to which adequacy of the foreseen privacy protection provisions are verified by functional means and not by any human based certification.

2 User needs and value proposition

The exploitation of the availability of medical data, and particularly in the context of AI, requires solutions to ensure continuous trust establishment, real time protection, value creation and value preservation as well as streamlined, human centered ways to empower individuals exercise their rights. These requirements are not only relating to the data subjects, otherwise the citizens, but also address the needs of other players such as data scientists, doctors and businesses that are the main entities that create value out of the data and also integrate this value in the appropriate supply and service chains that in the end return back to the society new and effective solutions. Examining each of these user types, PAROMA-MED analyzes their

needs and identifies the corresponding virtues and offerings of its solutions that aim to satisfy and increase the confidence of the particular user.

2.1 Data Subject

Starting with the data subject, PAROMA-MED identifies the fact that user centric solutions have to be made available for two main reasons. First to create privacy awareness in a simplified way, e.g. as it can be nowadays streamlined through the well adopted smartphone based practices (e.g push notifications/approvals and wallet apps), and secondly to engage users in the process of taking control of the value of their data either for protection purposes or for taking well informed decisions, e.g. for engaging with data altruism practices. Such transparency will be possible to eliminate both the fears that may lead to high protectionism but also, the other extreme, the complete and unrestricted neglectful attitudes towards data related rights. Therefore, PAROMA-MED intends to satisfy the need of the individual to be sure that their options are fully respected and enforced. In order to do that, the project plans to offer the means that empower the individual with personalized and well informed views. Through these interfaces citizens can exercise their rights with the main feature being an assisted consent management that enables well informed decisions but also friendly ways to even negotiate with the user additional permissions on demand, e.g. for usages not known in advance. In total the data subject will be fully aware and able to review any entity, process, the timing and the purposes relating to the processes their data had been or can be involved.

2.2 Data Scientist

Identifying next the data scientist as a vital player in value creation, PAROMA-MED targets directly the fundamental requirement for rich data availability with high quality as a key aspect for the exploitation of the high potential of AI. At the same time, it identifies that the eagerness for access to data might overlook any required restrictions from GDPR point of view and other relevant data acts and that dealing with such details consumes valuable time from the involved scientists and may delay the evolution of significant solutions. Additionally, it is evident that the value data scientists create (in the form of new ML models) has to be equally protected. In order to address the requirements of the data scientist, PAROMA-MED offer data federation solution that may enable unlimited data sources to be made available or potentially available. From the moment creation/collection has been performed, storage will be coupled with consent options and almost at real time, information will be possible to be discovered for use in various training and usage scenarios. This is due to the fact that FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets) [1] principles are adopted in the data processing and storage pipelines under the continuous enforcement of the consent restrictions. This will offer the data scientist the possibility to query for data types availabilities and advance, without any other fear relating to legal constraints, their work as they will be sure that the used data will be accessed because consent enables it and most importantly the processing will take place in totally protected environment. Directly close to the data storage without the scientist struggling to collect and organise the data. Thereafter, the produced model falls within the same handling and protection like a any other data asset with managed and controllable life cycle.

2.3 Health Experts

Identifying the contribution of the domain knowledge as equally important as the primary data, PAROMA-MED in its effort to cater for user centric solutions, includes physicians in its user

list and considers their needs. Their role to create added value metadata on top of primary medical data can accelerate ML based processing and aid in reaching and discovering better and more targeted insights. On the other hand, in the era of AI, domain experts need to be able to contribute to value creation exploiting in this way their valuable knowledge. Obviously, physicians are, as data subjects do, concerned that their assets might be exploited without being in control or even informed. PAROMA-MED considers metadata as data assets and supports their interrelation with ownership as well as consent options. As such PAROMA-MED is able to support the traceability of the assets and finally to provide a complete overview of how such data are used.

2.4 Businesses and Organizations in Health Domain

The last type of user is actually the most sensitive one as it is also the main responsible regarding protection of sensitive information. These are the organizations that either participate in the process of data creation and storage, e.g. hospitals, medical centers, or utilize data in value chains relating to services and applications. Among their business purposes, data monetization is nowadays at the epicenter of their attention. Two things can be at stake for this type of users, exploitation of the value, and privacy breach for which they are legally responsible. Therefore they require that value is retained and remain under their control and that they do not risk any sensitive information disclosure. The strategic decision of PAROMA-MED is to implement edge based solutions that primarily restrict data movement and exchange. The value is created by engagement of local processing with assurance that the product of the processing is also protected and moved only among attested and verified modules in external domains. Overall, this can provide the assurance required by organizations and allow efficient and protected federation with protection provisions for both rights and value.

3 Concept

3.1 Data Spaces Ready

PAROMA-MED has identified Data Spaces as the vehicle to enable data sharing and maximum exploitation according to well defined and adopted sovereignty principles. Although Data Spaces are clearly tailored to the facilitation of data exchange among business stakeholders and domain specific ecosystems, the involvement of personal data, as in the case of healthcare, cannot be easily overcome. In a collection of position papers by the Data Space Business Committee [6], it is clearly stated that “a more open market for health data in Europe” is required by innovative companies to achieve scale as initiatives, like GAIA-X [7], cannot resolve the highly fragmented and heterogeneous EU health market as well as the issues stemming from differences in “interpretation and local legislative variations” of GDPR. For PAROMA-MED the core principle [10] for tackling with such challenges as well as for providing enabling solutions that can accelerate the adoption and scaling of Healthcare Data Spaces is closely related with the elimination of the need for actual private data exchange on the one hand, while on the other with enabling unrestricted utilisation and processing of private data directly inside the data storage facilities according to well articulated and accepted options set by the data subject [9].

Figure 1: Trust Establishment based on integrity of the participant

3.2 Trust Establishment

According to the European Data Strategy Fact Sheet [4] data processing moves gradually from centralised cloud computing facilities to smart connected and edge resources. This pattern in combination with Data Spaces leads to the formation of data federations where business domains attach to ecosystems in order to perform data related tasks according to specific roles [9]. According to GAIA-X conceptual model [5], participants interact within the federation by providing (producers) and consuming (consumers) resources. This type of relationship regards also data and it is fully aligned with PAROMA-MED. The basic assumption before engagement into a transaction is that all interacting parties present to each other verifiable credentials that have been issued by participants and signed by Trust Anchors. Aiming at enabling automated attestation of the federation participants, PAROMA-MED having followed closely the ideas of GAIA-X and the Compliance Service deployment options [8] (licensed, private decentralised, secure private and public decentralised models) intends to consolidate its trust establishment model on the grounds of the both the secure private model and the public decentralised model. The main features of the envisaged approach are:

- There is no manual process involved during trust establishment and legal binding (e.g. contracts and/or SLAs)
- Trust is based on proofs relating to the integrity of certified components and their exclusive involvement in privacy sensitive operations based on attestation by Trusted Execution Enclaves and/or Trusted Platform Modules
- Adherence to proper operation is a continuous process and verification failure leads to instant and immutable publication of the status change

3.3 Data Protection and Consent in the Loop

Adopting FAIR practices [1], from the moment data are generated or collected, PAROMA-MED foresees the utilisation of a FHIR [2] server and an object storage solution, both protected under the supervision and encryption of the trusted domain artifacts of edge nodes (Figure 1). The data collection flow ends with the secure storage of the medical results and the data subject information in a secure vault within the PAROMA-MED edge node. At this stage the data remain protected and associated with the identity of the subject but there are no options yet regarding how the data should be treated in terms of utilisation in a federated way.

Figure 2: Protection Layer

Next, PAROMA-MED platform identifies the absence of the consent for the newly collected information and notifies the subject to provide their preferences via wallet or web dashboard applications. User options are used to assemble a FHIR Consent Statement [3] that thereafter rules the way the particular data are treated. Once the consent options have been indicated, the trusted domain of the PAROMA-MED edge node filters the data access requests to ensure compliance with these options. In this way PAROMA-MED components create a protection layer that averts any action that is against the policy rules implied by the consent. This is either achieved by continuous evaluation of the intended actions or by assurance that the actions are performed by a trusted component. A positive evaluation results in enabling the execution of the action whereas a negative blocks it (Figure 2).

The role of the protection layer is not only to ensure that access to data is according to the policy stemming from the consent, it needs also to ensure that the artifact requesting the particular action/processing is also verifiable in terms of adherence to foreseen operation. Governance is exercised whenever data are to be used for some purpose. This can be done at the moment of data generation or whenever a not foreseen usage context is pending. Either due to initially limited usage policy or due to total absence of policy. In such case the subject is presented with an incoming request detailing the usage context so that a clear decision can be taken in the form of an enforceable policy. In that case, consent details are updated and the additional usage possibilities are allowed (Figure 3).

3.4 Data Federation

In order for data to be subject to usage in the context of particular actions, they have to be discoverable at least as far as federation purposes are concerned. For this purpose, a Data Inventory layer is produced out of the data types available inside the protected storage (Figure 4). Inventory updates are performed in batch mode to avoid statistical variation to be linked with certain identities. The flow to populate the content of the Data Inventory layer takes into account constraints from policies indicated by the individual consents. The overall result is subject to be published for discovery in a Data Space ecosystem through the appropriate Connector (Figure 5).

Figure 3: Dynamic Consent Updates

Figure 4: Data Inventory

3.5 Enabling Federated Learning

Once the data sources are exposed in the Data Space federation they can be utilised in AI model engineering. Exposure does not mean direct transfer to some external storage system but only the availability to be contributed to the resolutions of queries. Data scientists are able to query the federation for availability of types and volumes of data according to certain protection levels. The outcome is collected from all the participating domains. Each of the domains contributes to the query resolution by applying internally user policies and resolving the portions of the stored data that can be made available according to the query options (Figure 6).

This process aims at a streamlined and ergonomic approach that relieves the data scientists from the burden of locating data that are highly distributed, but most importantly from the burden of taking all measures to remain within the legal restrictions that private data protections legislation requires. This leads to an one stop shop service and enabling mechanism. At this stage availabilities are presented under three main categories (assuming local processing in all cases):

- Directly usable data
- Data of application relevance that need additional consent
- Data without known relevance and quantity

In case the first category suffices, the ML flow can continue. If not, the consuming side (Data Scientist on behalf of any organisation or only by themselves) can suggest rewards for the other

Figure 5: Data Space Exposure

Figure 6: Federated Query

two categories in an effort to secure adequate data availabilities for the proper development of the intended ML model. In such case the mechanisms described in section 3.3 may be activated. As the usage of data is constrained by the intentions and identity of the consumer based on the options of the producer or the subject the privacy of which is to be protected, there is need to firmly enclose the entire flow to be followed within the strict borders of an instantiated environment both in terms of deployed functionality and data with limited lifespan. The approach is based on GAIA-X Conceptual and Composition Module which foresees that resources can be [5]:

Figure 7: Data Usage Layer - Provisioning

- **Virtual Resource:** it represents static data in any form and necessary information such as dataset, configuration file, license, keypair, an AI model, neural network weights, . . .
- **Instantiated Virtual Resource:** it represents an instance of a Virtual Resource. It is equivalent to a Service Instance and is characterized by endpoints and access rights.

According to the envisaged approach, data at rest (stored in local Data Lake and FHIR server) are the Virtual Resources that can be instantiated within a volatile and isolated software enclosure where the intended processing is applied. This step requires that data are exposed in a uniform manner independently to the actual storage format forming a Data Usage Layer. Additionally, if this step requires certain filtering, encryption, anonymisation, watermarking to be applied, it is also performed during the provision phase of the Data Usage Layer (Figure 7). Once there is adequate data availability for the model training purposes, data are prepared and remain available for the foreseen processing (constrained in terms of usage and time limits).

4 Architecture

PAROMA-MED architecture follows the hybrid cloud pattern that foresees both centralised and local components with as much distribution and decentralisation of functionalities as possible. The decentralisation is considered as an enabling aspect to ensure both domain sovereignty and enough transparency to cater for all the constraints imposed by current and future legislation.

The architecture design (Figure 8) evolves by assuming that centralised and local/edge components contribute to the formation of three main categories of functionality (bottom up): i) An interconnection layer controlled by the Secure Path Computation controls logic that the project will deliver, ii) A data layer catering for all federation and ergonomic features to ease data application and service evolution on the hand, while on the other ensuring sovereign management of data assets through trusted operations, and iii) An application layer that eases deployment, operation and monitoring of application and service artifacts in the context of trust and transparency with privacy preservation at the core of the overall flows.

Figure 8: Architecture

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